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CONCEPT OF POPULATION POINTS AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION

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Abstract: Settlements in Uzbekistan are divided into cities, villages and towns depending on the production activity of the population.

A city is a settlement with less than 12,000 inhabitants, of which more than 15% can be associated with agriculture.

From 3,000 to 12,000 people live in workers' settlements. The population of Dacha settlements is at least 2 thousand people, more than 25% of them can be employed in agriculture. At least half of the population in resort villages are temporary residents - vacationers. Rural areas include settlements whose inhabitants are mainly engaged in agriculture.

Keywords: Settlements, city, extreme natural climate, streets, massifs, landscaping.

Settlements are usually permanent or temporary residences of people working in production enterprises and institutions located in a certain area. In addition, science and art workers live in settlements and serve the cultural and household needs of the population, etc.

Settlements in Uzbekistan are divided into cities, villages and towns depending on the production activity of the population.

A city is a settlement with less than 12,000 inhabitants, of which more than 15% can be associated with agriculture.

From 3,000 to 12,000 people live in workers' settlements. The population of Dacha settlements is at least 2 thousand people, more than 25% of them can be employed in agriculture. At least half of the population in resort villages are temporary residents - vacationers. Rural areas include

settlements whose inhabitants are mainly engaged in agriculture.

Based on the number of inhabitants, settlements are divided into:

- super-large cities (more than 3 million people);
- large cities (from 1 million to 3 million people);
- large cities (from 250 thousand to 1 million people);
- large cities (from 100 to 250 thousand people);
- medium-sized cities (from 50 to 100 thousand people);
- small towns and villages (from 5 thousand to 50 thousand people);
- large rural settlements (from 1 thousand to 5 thousand people);
- medium rural settlements (from 200 to 1 thousand people);

- small rural settlements (less than 200 people).

In addition, the Urban Development Code defines special regulatory objects:

- Tashkent city;
- Samarkand;
- cities - regional centers of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- spa towns;
- historical settlements, as well as settlements with historical and cultural monuments;
- urban and rural settlements with a separate living regime (military settlements, other closed administrative-territorial structures, settlements in state reserves, national parks, natural parks, etc.);
- urban and rural settlements located in areas with extremely unfavorable environmental conditions due to extreme natural-climatic conditions or radioactive pollution, increased seismicity, or are subject to man-made and natural emergency situations.

The location of settlements is the mutually agreed arrangement of streets, massifs, production, administrative, cultural and public buildings and landscaping facilities in accordance with the requirements of the rational organization of material production in this area for the functional organization of their territory.

Rational organization of the production zone in agricultural settlements, mechanization of production processes, and reduction of operating costs depend on proper placement. Therefore, in the establishment of agricultural enterprises, the settlement of rural settlements is of great economic importance. In addition to its economic importance, the arrangement must

meet technical, sanitary, zoo-hygienic and architectural requirements.

Figure 1. With the of a graph, explain the population growth curve when resources are (i) Limiting(ii) Not limiting.

Rural planning projects are closely related to the establishment of agricultural enterprises. The location of rural settlements is influenced by the social form of the economy and its size, on the basis of which the planning and design assignments for rural planning are drawn up.

The task of the planning project of the rural settlement is to determine the composition of the buildings and structures of the settlement and to determine the scheme of their placement in the territory, and in this regard, to organize the territory itself.

This problem is solved for each specific project object in accordance with its importance, current state and future development prospects, as well as taking into account all the local conditions of the area where it is located.

The best solution for a planning project is:

- creates the conditions for production, social activities and the daily life of the population to increase the maximum comfort and labor productivity;

- good sanitary and hygienic conditions for increasing labor productivity and household activities of the population;

- purposeful use of land area and proper consideration of all its natural features;

- the ability to implement the necessary measures for the improvement of the area (water supply, electrification, cleaning of the area, landscaping, etc.) in accordance with the purpose;

- cost-effectiveness and cheapness of planned planning, construction and improvement;

- beautiful appearance and architectural expressiveness of the entire settlement and its individual parts.

The main principles of the village planning project are as follows:

- provision of equal cultural and household conditions for city residents;

- reduction of unproductive losses of labor, time and money;

- taking into account the functional and technical characteristics of the object;

- taking into account the landscape and other natural features of the area;

- a combination of creative approach with technical elements.

The settlement is never stagnant, something is built, reconstructed and beautified based on the needs of the times.

The assessment of the area should be carried out sequentially according to the specific climatic region for each natural factor.

Comprehensive assessment is an analysis of the sum of natural factors and their influence on the selection of the area for the settlement of the city. In this case, it is necessary to take into account the climatic characteristics of the construction site: temperature, humidity, wind conditions, amount of precipitation, etc. It should be

remembered that they may differ depending on the topography, the presence of green areas and water areas. Therefore, for example, in regions with a humid climate, the places of elevations and hills are the most favorable for the placement of residential areas. In such conditions, quick removal of storm and melted surface water is ensured. In arid regions, on the contrary, according to microclimate indicators, lowlands can be favorable for the placement of residential buildings.

The wind regime has a significant influence on the selection of areas for residential and industrial zones and their mutual placement. For a given construction site, we construct a "wind flower" based on wind speed and frequency of occurrence in January and July. Taking into account the constructed graph of the wind regime, the residential zone should be located on the windward side of the prevailing winds compared to the industrial zone. In areas with opposite wind directions in summer and winter, residential buildings should be located to the left and right of the indicated wind directions in relation to industrial enterprises. In accordance with sanitary requirements, the industrial zone should be designed downstream of the residential area along the river if there is a water flow in the area.

If there is a large green area in the construction area, then it is advisable to move the residential area closer to it and use it as a recreation area for city residents. A small green area should be included in urban, functional zones as an element of urban improvement.

To determine the functional zones of the city, it is recommended to choose the most convenient areas. However, development of

disadvantaged areas should not be abandoned.

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